

1 **Inter-individual variation in provisioning rate, prey size and number, and links to total**
2 **prey biomass delivered to nestlings in the collared flycatcher *Ficedula albicollis***

3

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14 **Abstract**

15 **Background**

16 In bird species where offspring growth and survival rely on parents' food provisioning, parents
17 can maximise their fitness by increasing the quantity and/or the quality of preys delivered to
18 their offspring. Many studies have focused on inter-individual variation in feeding rate, yet this
19 measure may not accurately reflect the total amount of food (i.e. energy) provided by parents if
20 there is large variation in the quantity and quality of preys at each feeding. Here, we explored
21 the relative role of individual (sex, age, body condition), breeding (hatching date, brood size)
22 and environmental (temperature) factors on feeding rate, prey number, size and quality, and
23 their contribution to total prey biomass delivered to the nestlings of 164 collared flycatcher
24 (*Ficedula albicollis*) parents in 98 nests.

25 **Results**

26 Preys delivered to the nest were mainly larvae (53.6%) and flying insects (45.6%). Feeding rate
27 increased with brood size and age, and was higher in males than females. Mean prey number
28 decreased, but mean prey size increased, as the season progressed and parents feeding their
29 brood with primary larvae brought more preys per visit. Relationships between feeding rate,
30 mean prey number and size remained when taking into account the provisioning quality: parents
31 brought either a large number of small prey or a small number of larger items, and the force of
32 the trade-offs between feeding rate and mean prey number and size depended on the quality of
33 the provisioning of the parents. Whatever the percentage of larvae among preys in the
34 provisioning, the variance in total prey biomass was foremost explained by feeding rate (65.1%
35 to 76.6%) compared to mean prey number (16.4% to 26%) and prey size (2.7% to 4%).

36 **Conclusions**

37 Our study shows that variation in feeding rate, prey number, size, but not quality (i.e. percentage
38 of larvae), were influenced by individual factors (sex and age) and breeding decisions (brood

39 size and timing of breeding) and that, whatever the provisioning strategy adopted, feeding rate
40 was the best proxy of the total biomass delivered to the nestlings.

41

42 **Keywords**

43 Collared flycatcher, feeding rate, foraging, niche breadth, prey selection, provisioning strategy,
44 reproductive investment

45

46 **Background**

47 In birds, provisioning behaviour is strongly associated with reproductive success due to the
48 high-energy demands by young during the period of fast growth (Daunt et al. 2007; Austin et
49 al. 2020). To maximize the energy delivered to their young, parents can use different
50 nonexclusive provisioning behaviour strategies: they can (*a*) deliver preys at a fast rate, (*b*)
51 bring many prey items per foraging trip, (*c*) bring large items, and /or (*d*) deliver preys with
52 high energy and nutrient contents (Ramsay and Houston 2003; Sexton et al. 2017). Most of the
53 studies on provisioning behaviour so far have focused on the factors accounting for variations
54 in feeding rate (i.e. strategy *a*) (Christe et al. 1996; Moller and Jennions 2001). The sources of
55 variations in prey number, size and quality (strategies *b* to *d*) and their importance in shaping
56 the total amount of energy delivered to the nestlings remain less explored (Wright et al. 1998;
57 Mägi et al. 2009; Bowers et al. 2014; Funghi et al; 2019). For example, higher breeding success
58 could be counterintuitively associated to lower feeding rate when chicks are provisioned with
59 higher quality preys and parents need less visits to reach offspring energy demands (Mägi et al.
60 2009). In this case, provisioning rate alone would not be a good proxy for breeding success.
61 Hence, studies exploring detailed provisioning strategies beyond measures of feeding rate are
62 needed in order to identify the main sources of variation in provisioning behaviour and test the

63 relative contribution of the different provisioning behavioural parameters to the total biomass
64 delivered to the nest. Furthermore, as provisioning strategies and energy fluxes can be
65 influenced by the trade-off between prey quality and quantity (Magrath et al. 2004; Mägi et al.
66 2009; Espindola-Hernandez et al. 2017), studies investigating the influence of prey quality on
67 quantitative metrics of provisioning rate (such as feeding rate, prey number and size) may help
68 to gain new insights on individual variation in provisioning strategies.

69 Inter-individual variation in provisioning has frequently been reported in birds. The
70 sources of variation can be broadly divided in at least three categories. First, variation in
71 provisioning can be related to individual factors such as sex, body condition, age and
72 experience. For example, males are often found to feed their young at lower rates than females,
73 which can be driven by their uncertainty in paternity (Sheldon and Ellegren 1998; Gao et al.
74 2019). Parental effort may also be traded against body condition maintenance due to the trade-
75 off in the allocation of limited energy between current and future reproduction (Verhulst and
76 Nilsson 2008). Individuals may also increase reproductive effort when reaching old ages, to
77 maximise their last reproductive output (Pärt et al. 1992; Froy et al. 2013), or when
78 inexperienced, to reach the chicks' energy demands (Cichoń 2003). Inter-individual differences
79 in cognitive abilities might also shape variation in provisioning behaviour because skills such
80 as searching for, catching and handling preys might have to be learned so that wiser birds may
81 demonstrate a higher foraging efficiency (Rutz et al. 2006; Cauchard et al. 2017; McLeay et al.
82 2017; Franks and Thorogood 2018). Second, variation in provisioning behaviour can also arise
83 from breeding decisions such as the timing of breeding and the number of chicks to feed.
84 Indeed, individuals starting breeding earlier might secure higher quality breeding sites /
85 territories (Kokko, 1999), although breeding in synchrony (i.e. not too early or too late) with
86 the peak of food resources determines the access to food resources (Both et al. 2006; Verhulst
87 and Nilsson 2008). Furthermore, parents of large broods could maximise the energy delivered
88 to the brood by concentrating on caterpillars (Moreno et al. 1995) rather than nutritious (as they

89 contain more of the amino acid taurine important of nestling development; Ramsay and
90 Houston 2003) but low energy contents spiders (Wiebe and Slagsvold 2015; Espindola-
91 Hernandez et al. 2017). Finally, environmental factors such as temperature or rainfall are likely
92 to influence provisioning by affecting both parent's ability to forage (Sanz and Tinbergen 1999;
93 McKechnie & Wolf, 2010; Wiley & Ridley 2016) and prey availability (Funghi et al; 2019;
94 Vincens and Bosch 2000).

95 In this study, we explored the relative role of individual factors (sex, age, body condition),
96 breeding decisions (timing of the season, brood size) and environmental factors (temperature)
97 on feeding rate, number, size and type of preys delivered to the nestlings in a wild population
98 of collared flycatchers (*Ficedula albicollis*). Collared flycatchers typically prey on flying
99 insects on the wing, but during the rearing period, they also forage on the foliage and on the
100 ground for caterpillars and other crawling insects (Gustafsson 1989), which both have a higher
101 energy content than flying insects and require less energy to capture (Barba et al. 1996).
102 Because provisioning parameters such as feeding rate, number and size of preys can differ
103 across individuals based on the quality of their provisioning (e.g. percentage of larvae among
104 preys, Espindola-Hernandez et al. 2017), we first investigated the individual, breeding and
105 environmental factors influencing the percentage of larvae among preys. Then, we controlled
106 for this percentage of larvae when analysing individual variation in feeding rate, number and
107 size of preys depending on the same individual, breeding and environmental, factors. This
108 approach allowed us to examine to what extent feeding rate alone, which is widely used in the
109 literature as a non-invasive proxy of food intake, provides a reliable measure of the quality and
110 quantity of the prey biomass delivered to the nestlings.

111

112 **Results**

113 Provisioning behaviour was recorded during 80 minutes on 98 nests, corresponding to 164
114 parents actively provisioning their chicks (95 females and 69 males). The main prey items

115 delivered to the nestlings were larvae (53.6%; 2033 out of 3795 preys) followed by flying
116 insects (45.6%; 1731 preys). Spiders and preys that could not be classified represented less than
117 1% of the preys (23 spiders and 8 non-classified).

118

119 **Factors influencing the proportion of larvae delivered to the nestlings**

120 Although the proportion of larvae delivered to the nestlings greatly varied across individuals
121 (Fig. 1), none of the individual, breeding and environmental factors considered in this study
122 significantly explained variation in this trait (all *P*- values > 0.1; Table 1).

123

124 **Factors influencing provisioning variables**

125 Feeding rate per hour increased significantly with brood size (mean scaled estimate [95% CI]
126 = 2.50 [1.67; 3.33]; Fig. 2A), was higher in males compared to females (-2.05 [-3.96; -0.15];
127 Fig. 2B) and in 2 years old or older adults compared to yearlings (2.00 [0.25; 3.76]; Fig 2C).
128 The feeding rate was neither influenced by the percentage of larvae among the preys (-0.69 [-
129 0.56; 0.18]), nor by adult body condition (0.19 [-0.76; 1.15]), hatching date (0.41 [-0.43; 1.25])
130 and ambient temperature (-0.05 [-0.84; 0.75]) (Table 1).

131 The mean number of preys delivered to the nestlings per visit was significantly explained
132 by the percentage of larvae among the preys (mean scaled estimate [95% CI] = 0.13 [0.04;
133 0.22]; Fig. 3A) and hatching date (-0.13 [-0.23; -0.03]; Fig. 3B): parents feeding their brood
134 with primary larvae brought more preys per visit and parents delivered less preys as the
135 breeding season progressed. None of the other variables influenced the mean number of preys:
136 sex (-0.05 [-0.02; 0.12]), age (-0.11 [-0.30; 0.08]), body condition (-0.06 [-0.16; 0.04]), brood
137 size (0.01 [-0.08; 0.11]) or ambient temperature (0.09 [-0.00; 0.18]) (Table 1).

138 Finally, mean prey size increased with hatching date (mean scaled estimate [95% CI] =
139 0.09 [0.03; 0.15]; Fig. 4): parents brought bigger preys as the breeding season progressed. Mean
140 prey size also tended to increase with age (0.13 [-0.00; 0.27]) (Table 1). None of the other

141 variables influenced the mean number of preys: sex (-0.04 [-0.08; 0.16]), body condition (0.05
142 [-0.02; 0.12]), brood size (-0.04 [-0.10; 0.02]), ambient temperature (-0.04 [-0.10; 0.01]) or the
143 percentage of larvae (-0.01 [-0.07; 0.06]) (Table 1).

144

145 **Table 1: Results of mixed models testing the effects of individual, breeding and**
 146 **environmental factors on provisioning parameters.**

Effect	DFNum	DFDen	t	P
Percentage of Larvae among the preys				
<i>Vresidual = 0.046 (N = 152). Vnestbox = 0.002 (N = 91). Varea = 0.025 (N = 13)</i>				
Sex[M]	1	88.1	-0.40	0.687
Age[Y]	1	134.3	-0.75	0.452
Body Condition	1	138.5	0.47	0.639
Hatching Date	1	85.6	-0.71	0.479
Brood size	1	89.9	-0.05	0.957
Ambient Temperature	1	76.4	0.73	0.466
Feeding Rate				
<i>Vresidual = 22.338 (N = 152). Vnestbox = 0.000 (N = 91). Varea = 3.688 (N = 13)</i>				
Sex[M]	1	137.2	2.24	0.027
Age[Y]	1	138.0	-2.11	0.036
Body Condition	1	142.1	0.39	0.693
Hatching Date	1	140.3	0.96	0.337
Brood size	1	141.1	5.90	< 0.001
Ambient Temperature	1	140.9	-0.12	0.905
% Larvae among the preys	1	132.0	-1.56	0.121
Mean Prey Number				
<i>Vresidual = 0.188 (N = 152). Vnestbox = 0.068 (N = 91). Varea = 0.039 (N = 13)</i>				
Sex[M]	1	82.7	-0.58	0.563
Age[Y]	1	124.0	-1.11	0.267
Body Condition	1	132.4	-1.23	0.220
Hatching Date	1	88.3	-2.65	0.009
Brood size	1	90.6	0.24	0.808
Ambient Temperature	1	80.2	1.88	0.064
% Larvae among the preys	1	127.7	2.90	0.004
Mean Prey Size				
<i>Vresidual = 0.112 (N = 152). Vnestbox = 0.002 (N = 91). Varea = 0.011 (N = 13)</i>				
Sex[M]	1	90.4	0.63	0.529
Age[Y]	1	137.3	1.92	0.056
Body Condition	1	142.7	1.38	0.168
Hatching Date	1	86.8	2.99	0.004
Brood size	1	93.5	-1.32	0.190
Ambient Temperature	1	84.0	-1.55	0.123
% Larvae among the preys	1	122.5	-0.21	0.832

147

148 The effect of sex is expressed as Males versus Females, and the effect of age as Yearling versus
 149 Older adults. Two-way interactions between sex and age, on the one hand, and the other fixed
 150 effects, on the other hand were not significant and removed from the final models. Significant
 151 fixed effects are reported in bold. Analyses were ran on 152 individuals (85 females and 67
 152 males) with complete information for all the explanatory variables.

153 **Relationships between provisioning variables**

154 We examined the relationships between mean prey size, number and feeding rate while taking
155 into account for the quality of prey items provisioned by the parents (i.e. percentage of larvae).
156 The first and second tertile in the distribution of the percentage of larvae brought to the nest
157 were at 44.4% and 66.7% (Fig. 1). Thus, we compared the relationships between provisioning
158 variables in parents provisioning their chicks with <44.4% of larvae in the preys (lower tertile;
159 $n= 54$ parents) versus parents provisioning their chicks between 44.4% and 66.7% of larvae in
160 the preys (middle tertile; $n = 53$ parents) versus parents provisioning their chicks with > 66.7%
161 of larvae in the preys (upper tertile; $n = 57$ parents).

162 Results show a strong trade-off between the mean prey number and mean prey size per
163 visit for a given parent independently of the percentage of larvae in the preys (Table 2). Thus,
164 for each visit, parents provisioned either large numbers of small prey items or small numbers
165 of large items (Fig. 5A). There was evidence for a significant trade-off between feeding rate
166 and mean number of preys brought per visit in parents bringing a mixed of larvae and other
167 insects to their offspring (Table 2), those parents making either fewer visits with many prey
168 items per visit or many visits with few prey items per visit (Fig. 5B). Finally, there was also
169 evidence for a trade-off between feeding rate and mean prey size foremost apparent in parents
170 bringing mostly larvae among the preys (Table 2), those parents making either few visits with
171 large prey items per visit or many visits with small prey items per visit (Fig. 5C).

172

173 **Table 2. Results of Pearson’s correlations between provisioning parameters depending on**
 174 **the percentage of larvae among the preys delivered to the nestlings in one hour.**

	Percentage of larvae among the preys								
	1 st tertile (few larvae)			2 nd tertile (mixed)			3 rd tertile (many larvae)		
	<i>N</i> = 54			<i>N</i> = 53			<i>N</i> = 57		
	<i>r</i>	[95% CI]	<i>P</i>	<i>r</i>	[95% CI]	<i>P</i>	<i>r</i>	[95% CI]	<i>P</i>
prey size - prey number	-0,692	[-0.810; -0.522]	<0.001	-0,640	[-0.776; -0.447]	<0.001	-0,404	[-0.601; -0.160]	0,002
prey number - feeding rate	-0,172	[-0.420; 0.100]	0,217	-0,330	[-0.545; -0.057]	0,017	-0,045	[-0.302; 0.218]	0,743
prey size - feeding rate	-0,237	[-0.475; 0.032]	0,087	-0,217	[-0.461; 0.056]	0,122	-0,335	[-0.548; -0.081]	0,012

180 Significant fixed effects are reported in bold. Data are divided in 3 tertiles, depending on
 181 whether a parent was bringing few larvae (1st tertile; < 44.3%), a mixed of larvae and other
 182 preys (2nd tertile; 44.3% - 66.7%), or mostly larvae (3rd tertile; > 66.7%). Data are on 164
 183 individuals.

184 **Provisioning variables explaining the total prey biomass delivered to the nestlings**

185 Whatever the percentage of larvae delivered to the nestlings by a parent, the variance in total
186 prey biomass per hour delivered to the nestlings was mainly explained by variation in feeding
187 rate (65.1% to 67.6%; Table 3): parents provisioning their chicks with few larvae, a mixed
188 percentage of larvae, or many larvae, increased their total prey biomass delivered to the
189 nestlings while increasing their feeding rate (respectively: mean scaled estimate [95% CI] =
190 0.88 [0.79; 0.97], 1.03 [0.97; 1.08], 0.85 [0.78; 0.92]). The variance in total prey biomass was
191 also significantly explained by mean prey number and size delivered to the nestlings (Table 3),
192 but to a lower extent, with prey number explaining 16.4% to 26% of the variance and prey size
193 explaining 2.7% to 4.0% of the variance. Parents provisioning their chicks with few larvae, a
194 mixed percentage of larvae, or many larvae, increased their total prey biomass delivered to the
195 nestlings while increasing the number preys brought per feeding visit (respectively: mean scaled
196 estimate [95% CI] = 0.59 [0.47; 0.71], 0.60 [0.53; 0.67], 0.55 [0.48; 0.62]) and while increasing
197 the size of the preys (respectively: mean scaled estimate [95% CI] = 0.24 [0.11; 0.36], 0.29
198 [0.22; 0.36], 0.21 [0.14; 0.29]).

199

200 **Table 3: Anova tables reporting the contribution of feeding rate, prey number and size**
 201 **in the total amount of food delivered to the nestlings by parents.**

	Percentage of larvae among the preys														
	1st tertile (few larvae)					2nd tertile (mixed)					3rd tertile (many larvae)				
	Mean Sq	DF	F	P		Mean Sq	DF	F	P		Mean Sq	DF	F	P	
Feeding rate	38,40	1	362,51	<0.001	70,1%	48,71	1	1253,86	<0.001	76,6%	35,44	1	628,74	<0.001	65,1%
Prey number	9,55	1	90,14	<0.001	17,4%	10,43	1	268,58	<0.001	16,4%	14,15	1	250,93	<0.001	26,0%
Prey size	1,50	1	14,15	<0.001	2,7%	2,57	1	66,15	<0.001	4,0%	1,89	1	33,45	<0.001	3,5%
Residuals	5,30	50				1,90	49				2,99	53			

206 Data are divided in 3 tertiles, depending on whether a parent was bringing few larvae (1st tertile;
 207 < 44.3%), a mixed of larvae and other preys (2nd tertile; 44.3% - 66.7%), or mostly larvae (3rd
 208 tertile; > 66.7%). Data are on 164 individuals.

209 **Discussion**

210 In this study, we examined to what extent individual, breeding and environmental factors
211 influence parental provisioning strategies, and investigated the relative contribution of feeding
212 rate, prey number and size in influencing the total prey biomass delivered to the nestlings. We
213 found collared flycatcher parents to provision their chicks mainly with larvae (53.6%) and
214 flying insects (45.6%).

215 We found that neither sex, age, body condition, hatching date, brood size or temperature
216 influenced the percentage of larvae among the preys, even if we found a great inter-individual
217 variation in this percentage (Figure 1). This result could seem surprising, since previous studies
218 found flycatcher's diet to vary with time or sex. Parent collared flycatchers were reported to
219 bring mostly caterpillars over other preys when caterpillar abundance is high around the second
220 half of May (Török and Tóth 1988). In the closely related Pied Flycatcher *Ficedula hypoleuca*,
221 one study reported that females foraged on caterpillars in the tree canopy and males on flying
222 insects caught the wings (Mänd et al. 2013), whereas no differences between sexes in prey types
223 were found in two other studies (Moreno et al 1995, Siikamäki et al., 1998). Interestingly, the
224 sex difference in foraging niche reported by Mänd et al. (2013) was reduced when
225 environmental conditions became worse (i.e. experimentally increased level of hunger of
226 nestlings). Since the environmental conditions experienced by our population in spring 2015
227 were relatively unfavourable (i.e. reproductive success in 2015 was lower than in other years,
228 pers. obs.), we cannot exclude that we could have found sex and timing of breeding differences
229 if the study was performed under different conditions. Individuals might also learn specific prey
230 choices throughout their life, so that older birds may select more profitable prey types for
231 nestlings (Forslund and Pärt 1995; Wiebe and Slagsvold 2015). However, again, we did not
232 observe any difference with age in our study although a large sample size on very old birds (4
233 years old and older) would be needed to look at senescence in provisioning parameters in this
234 species.

235 As previously found in the literature, feeding rate increased mainly with brood size: the
236 more chicks there are the more food parents have to bring back to the nest (Sanz and Tinbergen
237 1999), including for experimentally enlarged broods (Sendecka et al. 2007). We also found
238 feeding rate to increase with age, in line with previous studies in collared flycatchers and other
239 bird species (Pärt et al. 1992; Cichoń 2003; Froy et al. 2013). This is either because birds may
240 increase reproductive effort when reaching old ages to maximise their last reproductive output
241 (Froy et al. 2013), or because young birds may show a reduced experience in provisioning
242 (Cichoń 2003) or in securing high quality territories / sites with high quality prey (Slotow and
243 Rothstein 1991; Franks & Thorogood 2018). Feeding rate also varied with sex, but we found
244 males to provision their young more often than females. This result can be surprising, as the
245 reverse is usually found in the literature in species with biparental care (review in Lewis et al.
246 2002 for seabirds and Kilner 2002 for passerine); however, no difference is often reported too
247 (Moreno et al. 1995; Peck and Congdon 2006). Differences in feeding rate between sexes can
248 arise if males engage in activities such as nest/territory defence against competitors at the
249 expense of parental care (Qvarnström 1997) or males reduce their parental effort when being
250 uncertain about their paternity in species with extra-pair mating, such as the Collared flycatcher
251 (Gao et al. 2019). Our result is likely due to the timing of our video recordings: we recorded
252 provisioning early in the morning during the nestling rearing period when females, on top of
253 provisioning, still partly brood nestlings that do not fully thermoregulate yet, while males only
254 provision nestlings (Schwagmeyer et al. 1999). Accordingly, on our videos, males were
255 observed from time to time delivering the prey items that they brought back to the brooding
256 female inside the nest box, and the female then delivered the food to the young. This behaviour
257 both increased the feeding rate of males that were saving time on each visit and decreased the
258 feeding rate of females that were spending more time in the nest box. In our study, the feeding
259 rate was not influenced by the timing of the breeding (i.e. hatching date) nor by the percentage
260 of larvae among the preys. However, our results showed that mean prey size and number per

261 visit varied with the timing of the breeding, as previously found in the literature in various
262 species too (Bowers et al. 2014), and the percentage of larvae among the preys: parents that fed
263 their young mostly with larvae (i.e. > 77%) brought more preys per visit. Although, we cannot
264 exclude that using only prey length, and thus ignoring their width, height as well as their mass,
265 may have led to a low accurate estimate of prey size.

266 We then compared the relationship between feeding rate, mean prey size and number per
267 visit, taking into account the percentage of larvae among the preys brought by the parent.
268 Parents with low, medium and high percentage of larvae in their provisioning showed negative
269 correlation between the mean prey number and size per visit, as previously found in the
270 literature (Siikamäki et al., 1998; Wright et al. 1998). However, the feeding rate itself increased
271 when mean prey number decreased, a trade-off that was foremost apparent in parents with a
272 mixed percentage of larvae during provisioning: these parents made either few visits with many
273 prey items per visit or many visits with few prey items per visit. In parents provisioning their
274 brood mainly with larvae or flying insects, the relationships between feeding rate and prey
275 number were negative, but not significantly so. We also found feeding rate to increase when
276 mean prey size decrease, but mainly in parents with a high percentage of larvae during
277 provisioning: these parents made either few visits with large prey items per visit or many visits
278 with small prey items per visit. These results support the hypothesis that quantitative measures
279 of provisioning strategies (i.e. feeding rate, prey number and size) can be influenced by
280 variation in prey quality, as previously reported in the three other insectivorous birds: the brown
281 songlark (*Cincloramphus cruralis*) (Magrath et al. 2004), the great tit (*Parus major*) (Mägi et
282 al. 2009) and the thorn-tailed rayadito (*Aphrastura spinicauda*) (Espindola-Hernandez et al.
283 2017). In the present study, prey quality had nonetheless only minor consequences on variation
284 in provisioning strategies. This might be partly explained by the crude measure of quality
285 (larvae versus flying) that we used, and ideally information per type of prey on energy content

286 as well as search and handling time should be used to build an index of prey quality (Barba et
287 al. 1996; Mägi et al. 2009; Espindola-Hernandez et al. 2017).

288 Finally, whatever the percentage of larvae among the preys delivered to the nestlings, the
289 total prey biomass was mainly influenced by the feeding rate: 70.1%, 76.6% and 65.1% of the
290 total prey biomass variance was explained by the feeding rate of parents provisioning their
291 chicks with low, mixed or many larvae respectively. Mean prey number explained a lesser part
292 of this variation, explaining 17.4%, 16.4% and 26.0% respectively. As for mean prey size, it
293 only explained a negligible part of the total biomass, i.e. 2.7%, 4.0% and 3.5% of the variance.
294 Although nestlings' differences in food requirements and in begging behaviour due to sexual
295 differences might influence inter-individual chicks' difference in food intake (Espíndola-
296 Hernández et al. 2017), these results support the use of feeding rate as a good non-invasive
297 proxy of nestlings total food intake during rearing. Our estimate of biomass is based however
298 on estimates of size from pictures, and future studies are needed to validate this crude estimate
299 as an accurate measure of biomass in g per se.

300 Besides individual and breeding factors, environmental factors such as meteorological
301 conditions should influence provisioning performance by affecting both parent's ability to
302 forage and prey availability (Funghi et al; 2019). For example, poor environmental conditions,
303 as reflected by low temperature, might affect birds' abilities to locate preferred prey types
304 and/or increase the energetic cost of looking for prey items. Indeed, low temperatures reduce
305 ectothermic preys' metabolism and thus growth and activity for caterpillars, flying insects and
306 spiders (Vincens and Bosch 2000). Moreover, foraging in colder weather is more energy
307 demanding for parents for maintaining both body temperature and activity level (Sanz and
308 Tinbergen 1999), so that birds may not be able to invest as much energy in provisioning
309 compared to warmer days. In the same way, high temperature can cause a stress to breeders that
310 rapidly exceed their physiological tolerance limits (McKechnie & Wolf, 2010) and affect their
311 investment in young (Wiley & Ridley 2016). In our study, environmental factors showed only

312 a small, non-significant, contribution to variation in provisioning traits: only the mean number
313 of preys tended to be affected by temperature, with parents bringing more prey items per visit
314 on warmer days. During our study, daily temperature ranged from 11.6°C to 14.8°C, and it is
315 thus possible that variance was too small in our sample to detect an effect. We were not able to
316 quantify the influence of rainfall because provisioning behaviour was not recorded during heavy
317 rain days, to avoid the risk of further disturbance for the parents known to be in difficult
318 conditions already (our personal observations showed that provisioning was strongly reduced
319 in periods of heavy rain).

320

321 **Conclusions**

322 We investigated simultaneously individual, breeding and environmental factors to better
323 understand their effect on collared flycatchers provisioning performance. While brood size, sex
324 and age explained variation in feeding rate, only hatching date and the quality of the
325 provisioning explained variation in mean prey number and size per visit. Despite the trade-off
326 in provisioning strategies between prey number and size (i.e. parents make either few visits
327 with many or large prey items per visit, or many visits with few or small prey items per visit),
328 and between feeding rate and mean prey number/size under certain conditions, the total prey
329 biomass brought per hour to the nest was mainly influenced by feeding rate. This result supports
330 the use of feeding rate as an important measure of provisioning in the avian literature.

331

332 **Methodology**

333 **Study site and population monitoring**

334 The study was conducted on 164 (95 females and 69 males, corresponding to 98 nests) collared
335 flycatchers, breeding on the island of Gotland, Sweden (57°07' N, 18°20' E) between April and
336 July 2015. This patchy population of small, migratory hole-nesting passerine birds has been
337 monitored each year since 1980. Flycatchers readily accept to breed in artificial nest boxes,

338 providing an easy access to recording breeding data and behaviour at the nest (Doligez et al.
339 2004). Collared flycatchers display biparental care and feed on average 3 to 5 young from late
340 May to early July during 16 days until fledging.

341 Nests were visited at least every four days to collect data on laying and hatching dates,
342 clutch and brood size (at day 8, 2-3 days after provisioning videos), and final breeding success.
343 When chicks were 8 to 14 days old, adults were caught and identified using individually
344 numbered rings. They were sexed (based on plumage sexual dimorphism (i.e. males are black
345 and white while females are brownish) and aged (yearling vs. 2 years old or older, based on
346 plumage characteristics, Svensson 1992), and measured (tarsus length, to the nearest 0.1 mm,
347 and body mass, to the nearest 0.1 g). Body condition was computed as the body mass divided
348 by tarsus length (Doligez et al. 2004).

349 Data on daily temperature were obtained from the weather centre 02679 in Hoburgen,
350 Gotland (56° 55' N, 18° 09' E; 36 m), which is located around 20 km from our field site. We
351 used the mean daily temperature in Celsius degrees.

352

353 **Food provisioning**

354 Food provisioning behaviour was recorded during 1h20 between 06:00 and 13:00
355 (previous study in the same population showed no variation in the provisioning rate using the
356 same temporal window; Sheldon et al. 1997) when nestlings were 5-6 days old, i.e. during the
357 peak of daily parental activity and nestling growth (Krist et al. 2004; Rosivall et al. 2009). An
358 IR camera was installed in the nest box on the day before the recording to let birds habituate to
359 the device. Videos to be analyzed were randomly attributed between two observers (EIM and
360 RL) blind to the individual and environmental variables subsequently used in statistical models.
361 Using the motion-detection software programme Motion Meerkat (Weinstein 2015), we
362 recorded for each parental visit the following parameters: (i) entrance and exit time, (ii) number
363 of preys delivered, (ii) prey categories divided into 4 groups: caterpillar, flying insect, spider or

364 undetermined, (iii) prey size on a scale of 1-4, with 1 for preys smaller than beak length, 2 for
365 preys of about beak length, 3 for preys twice longer than beak length and 4 for preys three times
366 longer than beak length or bigger.

367 For each individual, we extracted five descriptors of provisioning behaviour: a) mean
368 number of prey per visit, b) mean prey size per visit, c) feeding rate per hour, computed as the
369 total number of feeding visits that occurred from the time the bird first appeared on the video
370 until the end of the video divided by the time interval in hours, d) total prey biomass delivered
371 to the nestlings per hour, computed as *mean number of prey per visit* ×
372 *mean size of prey per visit* × *feeding rate per hour*, and e) the percentage of larvae over the
373 total number of preys delivered to the nestlings per hour .

374 Preliminary analyses of 147 visits by the two observers showed that they differ in how
375 they scored prey number and size per visit: one observer counted more preys (paired t-test: $t_{146} =$
376 -4.00 , $P < 0.001$; mean [95%CI] difference = 0.35 [0.18 ; 0.53]) but sized preys as smaller ($t_{146} =$
377 8.69 , $P < 0.001$; -0.50 [-0.61 ; -0.38]) than the other observer. There were no differences in the
378 prey category. Hence, we standardized mean prey size and mean prey number using mean
379 differences between observers as correction factors for subsequent statistical analyses.

380

381 **Statistical analyses**

382 The quality of the food delivered to the nestlings by a parent can influence his strategy (i.e.
383 provisioning frequency and number/size/type of items per visit). We thus first examined the
384 variation of the proportion of larvae delivered to the nestlings and controlled for it when further
385 investigating the individual and environmental factors on provisioning parameters.

386 We investigated the influence of individual and environmental factors on provisioning
387 behaviour by running 3 sets of generalised linear mixed effect models with (i) mean prey
388 number per visit, (ii) mean prey size per visit and (iii) feeding rate. We included as random
389 effects the forest patch to account for potential spatial variation in prey availability and nest box

390 to account for the non-independence of both parents in a pair. We included sex, age, body
391 condition, hatching date, brood size at day 8, mean daily temperature and the percentage of
392 larvae as fixed variables, plus all possible two-way interactions between sex or age and the
393 other fixed effects. Interactions were removed from the models if non-significant.

394 We then characterized food provisioning strategies by assessing partial correlations
395 between mean prey number and size per visit and provisioning rate. To outline differences when
396 looking for provisioning quantity or quality, we divided parents in 3 categories depending on
397 whether they were bringing few larvae in the preys, a mix of larvae and other insects, or mostly
398 larvae. We used tertiles in the percentage of larvae in the preys to build up our 3 categories.

399 Finally, we assessed the relative contributions of mean prey number and size per visit
400 and feeding rate to the total prey biomass delivered to the nestlings per hour using used multiple
401 linear regression models. We split the analyses in parents provisioning their nest with larvae in
402 the preys, a mix of larvae and other insects, or mostly larvae, to investigate whether the type of
403 preys brought influenced the relationships between provisioning variables and total prey
404 biomass delivered to the nestlings.

405 Data analyses were carried out in the version 3.5.0 of the statistical freeware R cran (R
406 Core Team 2016). Continuous explanatory variables were scaled before analysis to improve the
407 interpretability of our model estimates (Schielzeth 2010). Mean estimates and 95% confidence
408 intervals are reported in the results; intervals that do not overlap with 0 are considered as
409 significant.

410

411 **Declarations**

412 Birds were caught, handled and ringed under a licence from the Stockholm Museum Ringing
413 Centre (license number 471:M015 to B.D.) and behavioural tests were conducted in accordance
414 with the Swedish legal requirements applicable in the year of the study. The authors declare
415 that they have no competing interest. This work was supported by grants from the CNRS (PICS)

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420 designed the study, LC and BD collected data in the field, EIM, RL and PB analysed videos,
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425

426 **References**

427 Austin SH, Robinson WD, Robinson TR, Ellis VA, Ricklefs RE. Development syndromes in
428 New World temperate and tropical songbirds. *PLoS One*. 2020;15:e0233627.

429 Barba E, López JA, Gil-Delgado JA. Prey preparation by adult Great Tits *Parus major* feeding
430 nestlings. *Ibis*. 1996; 138: 532-8.

431 Both C, Bouwhuis S, Lessells CM, Visser ME. Climate change and population declines in a
432 long-distance migratory bird. *Nature*. 2006; 441: 81-3.

433 Bowers EK, Nietz D, Thompson CF, Sakaluk SK. Parental provisioning in house wrens: effects
434 of varying brood size and consequences for offspring. *Behavioral Ecology*. 2014; 25:1485-93.

435 Cauchard L, Angers B, Boogert NJ, Lenarth M, Bize P, Doligez B. An Experimental Test of a
436 Causal Link between Problem-Solving Performance and Reproductive Success in Wild Great
437 Tits. *Frontiers in Ecology and Evolution*. 2017; 5: 107.

438 Christe P, Richner H, Oppliger A. Begging, food provisioning, and nestling competition in great
439 tit broods infested with ectoparasites. *Behavioral Ecology*. 1996; 7 :127-31.

440 Cichoñ M.. Does prior breeding experience improve reproductive success in collared flycatcher
441 females? *Oecologia*. 2003; 134: 78-81.

442 Daunt F, Wanless S, Harris MP, Money L, Monaghan P. Older and wiser: improvements in
443 breeding success are linked to better foraging performance in European shags. *Functional*
444 *Ecology*. 2007; 21: 561-7.

445 Doligez B, Part T, Danchin E. Prospecting in the collared flycatcher: gathering public
446 information for future breeding habitat selection? *Animal Behaviour*. 2004; 67: 457-466.

447 Espíndola-Hernández P, Castaño-Villa GJ, Vásquez RA, Quirici V. Sex-specific provisioning
448 of nutritious food items in relation to brood sex ratios in a non-dimorphic bird. *Behavioral*
449 *Ecology and Sociobiology*. 2017;71:1-8.

450 Franks VR, Thorogood R. Older and wiser? Age differences in foraging and learning by an
451 endangered passerine. *Behavioural Processes*. 2018; 148:1-9.

452 Froy H, Phillips RA, Wood AG, Nussey DH, Lewis S. Age-related variation in reproductive
453 traits in the wandering albatross: evidence for terminal improvement following
454 senescence. *Ecology Letters*. 2013; 16: 642-649.

455 Funghi C, McCowan LSC, Schuett W, Griffith SC. High air temperatures induce temporal,
456 spatial and social changes in the foraging behaviour of wild zebra finches. *Animal Behaviour*.
457 2019; 149:33-43.

458 Gao L-F, Zhang H-Y, Zhang W, Sun Y-H, Liang M-J, Du B. Effects of extra-pair paternity
459 and maternity on the provisioning strategies of the Azure-winged Magpie *Cyanopica cyanus*.
460 *Ibis*. 2020; 162: 627-36.

461 Gustafsson L. Collared Flycatcher. Lifetime Reproduction in Birds. I. Newton. London,
462 Academic Press. 1989; 75-88.

463 Kilner R. Sex differences in canary (*Serinus canaria*) provisioning rules. *Behavioral Ecology*
464 and *Sociobiology*. 2002; 52: 400-407.

465 Kokko H. Competition for early arrival in migratory birds. *Journal of Animal Ecology*. 1999;
466 68: 940-50.

467 Krist M, Remeš V, Uvírová L, Nádvorník P, Bures S. Egg size and offspring performance in
468 the Collared Flycatcher (*Ficedula albicollis*): a within-clutch approach. *Oecologia*. 2004; 140:
469 52-60.

470 Lewis S, Benvenuti S, Dall'Antonia L, Griffith R, Money L, Sherrat TN, Wanless S, Hamer
471 KC. Sex-specific foraging behaviour in a monomorphic seabird. *Proceedings of the Royal*
472 *Society of London Series B*. 2002; 269: 1687-1693

473 Mägi M, Mänd R, Tamm H, Sisask E, Kilgas P, Tilgar V. Low reproductive success of great
474 tits in the preferred habitat: A role of food availability. *Ecoscience*. 2009;16(2):145-57.

475 Magrath MJ, van Lieshout E, Visser GH, Komdeur J. Nutritional bias as a new mode of
476 adjusting sex allocation. *Proceedings of the Royal Society B*. 2004; 271 :S347-9.

477 McKechnie AE, Wolf BO. Climate change increases the likelihood of catastrophic avian
478 mortality events during extreme heat waves. *Biology Letters*. 2010; 6: 253-6.

479 McLeay LJ, Brad P, Goldsworthy D. But first, are you experienced? The consequences of
480 timing, age, and adult condition on reproductive performance in greater crested terns
481 *Thalasseus bergii*. *Marine Ornithology*. 2017; 45: 205-15.

482 Moller AP, Jennions MD. How important are direct fitness benefits of sexual selection?
483 *Naturwissenschaften*. 2001; 88: 401-15.

484 Moreno J, Cowie RJ, Sanz JJ, Williams RS. Differential Response by Males and Females to
485 Brood Manipulations in the Pied Flycatcher: Energy Expenditure and Nestling Diet. *Journal of*
486 *Animal Ecology*. 1995; 64: 721-32.

487 Pärt T, Gustafsson L, Moreno J. Terminal Investment and a Sexual Conflict in the Collared
488 Flycatcher (*Ficedula albicollis*). American Society of Naturalists. 1992; 140: 868-82. Peck DR,
489 Congdon BC. Sex-specific chick provisioning and diving behaviour in the wedge-tailed
490 shearwater *Puffinus pacificus*. J Avian Biol. 2006; 37 :245-51.

491 Qvarnström A. Experimentally increased badge size increases male competition and reduces
492 male parental care in the collared flycatcher. Proceedings of the Royal Society B. 1997; 264:
493 1225-1231.

494 R Core Team. 2016. R: a language and environment for statistical Computing

495 Ramsay SL, Houston DC. Amino acid composition of some woodland arthropods and its
496 implications for breeding tits and other passerines. Ibis. 2003;145:227-32.

497 Rosivall B, Szöllösi E, Hasselquist D, Török J. Effects of extrapair paternity and sex on
498 nestling growth and condition in the collared flycatcher, *Ficedula albicollis*. Animal
499 Behaviour. 2009; 77: 611-7.

500 Rutz C, Whittingham MJ, Newton M. Age-dependent diet choice in an avian top predator.
501 Proceedings of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences. 2006; 273: 579-86.

502 Sanz JJ, Tinbergen JM. Energy expenditure, nestling age, and brood size: an experimental study
503 of parental behavior in the great tit *Parus major*. Behavioral Ecology. 1999; 10: 598-606.

504 Schielzeth H. Simple means to improve the interpretability of regression coefficients. Methods
505 in Ecology and Evolution. 2010; 1: 103-113.

506 Schwagmeyer PL, Clair RCS, Moodie JD, Lamey TC. Species Differences in Male Parental
507 Care in Birds: A Reexamination of Correlates with male paternity. American Ornithological
508 Society. 1999; 116: 487-503.

509 Sendecka J, Cichoń M, Gustafsson L. Age-dependent reproductive costs and the role of
510 breeding skills in the Collared flycatcher. Acta Zoologica. 2007; 88: 95-100.

511 Sexton JP, Montiel J, Shay JE, Stephens MR, Slatyer RA. Evolution of Ecological Niche
512 Breadth. *Annual Review of Ecology, Evolution, and Systematics*. 2017; 48: 183-206.

513 Sheldon BC, Ellegren H. Paternal effort related to experimentally manipulated paternity of male
514 collared flycatchers. *Proceedings of the Royal Society of London Series B: Biological Sciences*.
515 1998; 265: 1737-42.

516 Sheldon BC, Räsänen K, Dias PC. Certainty of paternity and paternal effort in the collared
517 flycatcher. *Behavioral Ecology*. 1997; 8: 421-8.

518 Siikamäki P, Haimi J, Hovi M, Ratti O. Properties of food loads delivered to nestlings in the
519 pied flycatcher: Effects of Clutch Size Manipulation, Year, and Sex. *Oecologia*. 1998; 115:
520 579-85.

521 Slotow R, Rothstein SI. Importance of Dominance Status and Distance from Cover to
522 Foraging White-Crowned Sparrows: An Experimental Analysis. *The Auk*. 1995; 112: 107-17.

523 Svensson L. Identification guide to European passerines. Thetford: British Trust for
524 Ornithology; 1992.

525 Verhulst S, Nilsson J-Å. The timing of birds' breeding seasons: a review of experiments that
526 manipulated timing of breeding. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society B*. 2008; 363:
527 399-410.

528 Vicens N, Bosch J. Weather-dependent pollinator activity in an apple orchard, with special
529 reference to *Osmia cornuta* and *Apis mellifera* (Hymenoptera: Megachilidae and Apidae).
530 *Environmental Entomology*. 2000; 29: 413-420.

531 Weinstein BG. MotionMeerkat: integrating motion video detection and ecological monitoring..
532 *Methods in Ecology and Evolution*. 2015; 6.3; 357-62.

- 533 Wiebe KL, Slagsvold T. Foraging Trade-offs between Prey Size, Delivery Rate and Prey Type:
534 How Does Niche Breadth and Early Learning of the Foraging Niche Affect Food Delivery?.
535 *Ethology*. 2015; 121: 933-1029.
- 536 Wiley EM, Ridley AR. The effects of temperature on offspring provisioning in a cooperative
537 breeder. *Animal Behaviour*. 2016;117: 187-95.
- 538 Wright J, Both C, Cotton PA, Bryant D. Quality vs. Quantity: Energetic and Nutritional Trade-
539 Offs in Parental Provisioning. *British Ecological Society*. 1998; 67: 620-34.

540 **Figure legends**

541 **Figure 1: Distribution of the percentage of larvae among the preys delivered to the**
542 **nestlings in 80 minutes by parent collared flycatchers.** Data are on 164 parents (95 females
543 and 69 males).

544 **Figure 2: Feeding rate by parent collared flycatchers in relation to (A) brood size, (B) sex,**
545 **and (C) age category.** Data are on 152 individuals (85 females and 67 males).

546 **Figure 3: Number of prey per visit in relation to (A) the percentage of larvae among the**
547 **preys, (B) hatching date (1 is April 1st).** Data are on 152 individuals (85 females and 67
548 males).

549 **Figure 4: Mean prey size in relation to hatching date (1 is April 1st).** Data are on 152
550 individuals (85 females and 67 males).

551 **Figure 5: Mean prey size per visit in relation to (A) mean prey number, and (C) feeding**
552 **rate per hour; (B) represents mean prey number per visit in relation to feeding rate per**
553 **hour.** Data are on 164 parents (95 females and 69 males).